

ROLE IN HOUSE TRAINING AND ACADEMIC SUPERVISION IN IMPROVING TEACHER PERFORMANCE IN HIGH SCHOOL

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Abstract

Education is a dynamic sector that continually undergoes policy changes in line with societal demands and the pace of global development. These policy shifts directly impact the role of teachers, both in their pedagogical functions and in maintaining professional standards. Teachers are required to adapt to new regulations to perform their duties effectively. Failure to adapt may lead to decreased performance, ultimately affecting the quality of classroom learning. The implementation of the Merdeka Curriculum, which adopts a deep learning approach, demands teachers to adjust their competencies to carry out learning activities in accordance with its requirements. To address these challenges, the school implements In House Training (IHT) and academic supervision as strategies for professional teacher development. This study aims to analyze the role of IHT and academic supervision in improving teacher performance in the domain of pedagogical competence across three key aspects: lesson planning, instructional implementation, and learning evaluation. This research employs a qualitative case study approach, with data collected through in-depth interviews, classroom observations, and document analysis. The main informants include school supervisors, the school principal, the vice principal for curriculum, and teachers. The results indicate that IHT significantly enhances teachers' understanding of lesson plan development, differentiated instruction, and formative assessment. Meanwhile, academic supervision ensures the implementation of these competencies through pre-observation, classroom observation, reflection, and follow-up activities. Overall, there is a substantial improvement in teachers' abilities to design relevant instructional materials, apply active learning strategies, utilize digital media, and conduct more systematic learning assessments.

Keywords: In House Training (IHT), Academic Supervision, Teacher Performance, Lesson Planning, Learning Evaluation, Teacher Professional Development.

INTRODUCTION

Improving the quality of education at the senior high school (SMA) level is a top priority in the effort to create competent and competitive human resources in the global era. Teachers, as the spearhead of the learning process, play a key role in determining educational quality. Teacher performance is determined not only by teaching ability but also by the ability to plan lessons, implement effective learning strategies, and conduct comprehensive evaluations. Therefore, teacher professional development is crucial, particularly in the context of changing education policies and technological developments that demand teachers to continuously improve their competencies. Budi Mulia Karawang High School, as one of the private high schools in Karawang Regency, faces quite complex educational dynamics. Located in a rapidly developing environment, supported by an industrial area, the school also faces increasingly diverse learning needs. In recent years, Budi Mulia Karawang High School has committed to improving the quality of its teaching through various teacher professional development programs. This commitment is crucial given that internal school evaluations indicate varying teacher abilities in developing teaching materials, implementing project-based learning, and conducting authentic learning assessments in accordance with the demands of the Independent Curriculum. The implementation of the Independent Curriculum, which began in schools in the 2025/2026 academic year, requires teachers at SMA Budi Mulia Karawang to have stronger pedagogical competencies. Teachers must understand the concept of deep learning, apply a differentiated approach, utilize digital technology, and design student-centered learning. However, the reality on the ground shows that some teachers still struggle to align the curriculum with classroom learning planning and implementation. This competency gap is one of the school's main challenges.

To address these challenges, SMA Budi Mulia Karawang regularly implements an In-House Training (IHT) program as a form of internal training aimed at improving teachers' knowledge and skills. The IHT program is designed to provide an in-depth understanding of teaching aid development, active learning strategies, formative assessment, and technology integration in instruction. IHT serves as a collaborative platform for teachers to learn, discuss, and share best practices. In addition to the IHT (Instructional Instructional Teaching), the school also implements academic supervision conducted by the principal and supervisors from the education office. Academic supervision is conducted through pre-observation, classroom observation, reflection, and follow-up. Supervision serves not only as a monitoring mechanism but also as professional mentoring to help teachers improve their teaching performance. Supervision results indicate improvements in some teachers, but some teachers are still found to be inconsistent in implementing the IHT results and supervision recommendations.

This phenomenon demonstrates the need for an in-depth study of how IHT and academic supervision contribute to improving teacher performance at SMA Budi Mulia Karawang. Although the school has implemented both programs routinely, scientific evaluation of their effectiveness has not been widely conducted. This represents a significant research gap, given that improving teacher professionalism is a key factor in the successful implementation of the Independent Curriculum in schools. Thus, this research is relevant and important to conduct in the context of SMA Budi Mulia Karawang. Through this study, the authors attempt to comprehensively analyze how the implementation of IHT, and academic supervision contributes to improving teacher performance, particularly in the planning, implementation, and evaluation of learning. The research findings are expected to serve as a basis for schools to improve their teacher development strategies and create a higher-quality learning ecosystem.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In House Training (IHT)

The Ministry of Education and Culture, as quoted by (Kartika, 2023), explains that In-House Training (IHT) is a form of teacher professional development conducted internally within the school environment. This activity is designed to improve teachers' pedagogical, professional, social, and personal competencies according to real-world needs. According to the Ministry of Education and Culture, (Darling-Hammond & Hyler., 2020) emphasize that effective teacher training must be collaborative, practice-based, sustainable, and emphasize in-depth reflection. IHT fulfills these characteristics because it allows teachers to discuss, practice skills, and receive direct feedback from colleagues and internal sources such as principals, supervisors, or core teachers. IHT also serves as a means of increasing capacity in the implementation of the Independent Curriculum, particularly in the development of teaching modules, formative assessment, differentiated learning, and project-based learning. According to (Rahmawati, 2025), the successful implementation of the Independent Curriculum is largely determined by teachers' ability to develop relevant teaching materials and understand the philosophy of liberating learning. Thus, IHT is an important strategy for schools, especially SMA Budi Mulia Karawang, to improve teacher professionalism and support learning transformation.

Academic Supervision

According to Sari and Nugroho in (Abdurakhman, 2025), academic supervision is a systematic effort to ensure that teaching and learning activities run according to educational process standards. Academic supervision is carried out through a series of stages, starting from planning, and conducting observations, to follow-up in the form of reflection and coaching. Good supervision implementation not only assesses administrative aspects but also provides space for teachers to engage in professional dialogue with supervisors, thereby fostering a culture of learning and sharing experiences. In practice, academic supervision can use various approaches, such as directive, non-directive, and collaborative approaches. The directive approach is used when the supervisor is more active in providing direction and input to teachers, while the non-directive approach emphasizes open dialogue so that teachers find solutions independently. The collaborative approach combines both, where supervisors and teachers work together to plan learning improvements. According to Rahayu in (Saepudin, 2024), the collaborative approach has proven to be most effective because it creates a partnership and mutual trust between teachers and supervisors. Academic supervision plays a crucial role in developing teachers as lifelong learners. Through this activity, teachers receive constructive feedback to improve their pedagogical and professional skills. Mulyasa in (Muslim, 2023) emphasizes that supervision must be humanistic, democratic, and dialogical. Teachers are accompanied not to be judged, but to be helped to find solutions to learning problems. Academic supervision has been shown to improve teaching quality when implemented consistently, structured, and accompanied by follow-up (Sahertian, 2010). Academic supervision is a professional development process focused on improving the quality of learning through

mentoring and joint reflection between supervisors and teachers. Academic supervision serves not only as a control mechanism but also as a professional development tool that fosters a culture of learning in schools. Collaborative, ongoing, and needs-based supervision will produce teachers who are competent, creative, and adaptable to change. Therefore, strengthening supervisor capacity and a system for following up on supervision results are key to achieving sustainable educational quality in the Merdeka Belajar era. In the context of SMA Budi Mulia Karawang, academic supervision is a crucial instrument to ensure that teachers effectively implement the results of the IHT and improve the quality of classroom learning.

Improving Teacher Performance

According to (Uno & Lamatenggo, 2022) explain that performance (in the context of the teaching profession) is measurable behavior and work results within the function of the position; for teachers, it appears as evidence of instructional practices (planning, implementation, and assessment) and their impact on learning progress. According to (Priansa & Karwati, 2014) emphasize that learning planning is a fundamental component that determines the direction and success of the learning process. Teachers with good performance will be able to: develop relevant teaching materials (ATP, teaching modules, lesson plans), manage classes with active learning strategies, conduct authentic and formative assessments appropriately, and integrate digital technology into learning. According to (Guskey, 2021), improving teacher performance can only be achieved through two main steps: quality professional development and consistent learning evaluation mechanisms. Teachers who lack ongoing support tend to experience performance stagnation. Teacher performance at SMA Budi Mulia Karawang shows quite high variation, so it is important for the school to have a systematic coaching strategy through IHT and academic supervision.

METHOD

According to Rahardjo quoted (Arifudin, 2023) that the research method is one way to obtain and seek tentative truth, not absolute truth. The result is scientific truth. Scientific truth is a truth that is open to being tested, criticized, and even revised. Therefore, there is no best method for seeking truth, but what exists is the right method for a particular purpose according to the existing phenomenon. Budiharto quoted (Alammy, 2025) that the selection of research methods must be adjusted to the research being conducted so that the results are optimal. This study was conducted to examine the role of in-house training and academic supervision in improving teacher performance in high schools. The type of research used in this study is a case study method. According to Nursalam in (Rosmayati, 2025), a case study is research that includes an assessment aimed at providing a detailed description of the background, nature, and characteristics of a case. In other words, a case study focuses on a case intensively and in detail. Research in this method is carried out in depth on a situation or condition in a systematic manner, starting from making observations, collecting data, analyzing information, and reporting results.

The approach used in this research is a qualitative approach. According to Iskandar in (Maulana, 2025), a qualitative approach is where qualitative research as a scientific method is often used and implemented by groups of researchers in the social sciences, including educational science. Iskandar in (Ningsih, 2025) explains the qualitative research approach as a process of research and understanding based on methods that investigate social phenomena and human problems. This study employed qualitative research with field research methods. According to (Arifudin, 2025), this approach aligns with the primary objective of the study, which is to describe and analyze the role of in-house training and academic supervision in improving teacher performance in high schools. Therefore, this method will be able to explain the research problem (Aslan, 2025). According to Yin in (Kartika, 2025), the purpose of case study research is not simply to explain what the object of study is like but also to explain the circumstances and how the case occurred. Meanwhile, Waluya in (Sudrajat, 2024) states that the purpose of case studies is to develop in-depth knowledge about the object of study, meaning that this study is exploratory in nature.

Bogdan and Taylor in (Abduloh, 2020) explain that qualitative research methodology is a research procedure that produces descriptive data in the form of written or spoken words from people and observable behavior. In this study, researchers created a complex picture, examining words, detailed reports from respondents' views, and conducted studies in natural situations, specifically regarding the role of in-house training and academic supervision in improving teacher performance in high schools. Engineering can be seen as a means of carrying out technical work carefully using the mind to achieve goals. Although research is an endeavor within the scope of science, it is carried out to systematically collect realistic data to realize the truth. Research methodology is a means to find a solution to any problem. In this case, the author collected information on the role of in-house training and academic supervision in improving teacher performance in high schools, articles, journals, theses, ebooks, and others (Mukarom, 2024).

Because it requires library materials for its data sources, this research utilizes library research. Researchers require books, scientific articles, and other literature related to the topics and issues they are exploring, both printed and online (Romdoniyah, 2024). Seeking information from data sources requires the use of data collection techniques. Amir Hamzah in (Nasril, 2025) claims that data collection is an effort to gather information related to the topic being studied. The author used a library research method to collect data. Specifically, the author began with a library search to gather information from books, dictionaries, journals, encyclopedias, papers, periodicals, and other sources that shared insights into the role of in-house training and academic supervision in improving teacher performance in high schools. Furthermore, Amir Hamzah in (Delvina, 2020) states that data collection is defined as various efforts to gather facts related to a topic or discussion being or will be explored. These details can be found in scientific literature, research, scientific writings, dissertations, theses, and other written sources. According to (Aidah, 2024), data collection can be conducted in various circumstances, using different sources, and employing different techniques.

Observation is part of the research process that directly examines the phenomena being studied (Nita, 2025). This method allows researchers to directly observe and experience the atmosphere and conditions of the research subjects. The observations in this study focused on the role of in-house training and academic supervision in improving teacher performance in high schools. The interview technique in this study is a structured interview, namely an interview conducted using various established standard guidelines, questions are arranged according to information needs and each question is needed to reveal each empirical data (Afifah, 2024). Documentation is a data collection technique using existing written documents or records (Saepudin, 2022). Documentation comes from the word document, which means written objects. In implementing the documentation method, researchers investigate written objects, such as books, magazines, meeting minutes, and diaries. According to Moleong in (Widyastuti, 2024), the documentation method is a way of collecting information or data through examining archives and documents. Furthermore, according to (Sunasa, 2023), the documentation strategy is also a data collection technique proposed to research subjects. This data collection method using the documentation method is carried out to obtain data on the state of the institution (research object), namely the role of in-house training and academic supervision in improving teacher performance in high schools.

Moleong, quoted (Uswatiyah, 2023), explains that the collected data was analyzed using an interactive analysis model consisting of data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing. Syarifah et al. in (Kartika, 2022) explain that data reduction is carried out by filtering relevant information, presenting data in a systematic narrative form, and drawing conclusions based on research findings. To ensure data validity, this study used source triangulation, namely comparing information from sources. According to Moleong in (Saepudin, 2021), source triangulation helps increase the validity of research results by comparing various perspectives on the phenomenon being studied. According to Muhadjir in (Paramansyah, 2024), data analysis is the activity of systematically conducting, searching, and compiling records of findings through observation and interviews, allowing researchers to focus on the research they are studying. Afterward, the findings are turned into material for others, edited, classified, and presented. Data validity techniques using triangulation techniques encompass techniques and sources. Data analysis using the Miles and Huberman model in (Kartika, 2024) consists of data collection, data reduction, data presentation, and drawing conclusions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Result

Research on the implementation of In-House Training (IHT) and academic supervision at Budi Mulia Karawang High School has proven to significantly contribute to improving teacher competency and performance. The results are presented in six key findings as follows.

IHT Planning and Academic Supervision Based on Needs Analysis

The first finding indicates that IHT planning and academic supervision were conducted systematically and based on a teacher needs analysis. The needs analysis was obtained through educational reports, previous year's supervision results, teaching materials evaluations, and teacher reflections. The principal, vice principal for curriculum, and school supervisor were actively involved in developing this plan. The planning included establishing training objectives and targets, prioritizing materials, selecting resource persons, developing a schedule, and planning the budget. Information from interview documents demonstrates the consistency of this pattern. The principal stated that IHT planning begins with a needs analysis conducted through previous curriculum and supervision meetings. The supervisor also stated that the needs analysis was conducted by reviewing supervision results, educational reports, and curriculum development.

Implementation of IHT and Academic Supervision Improves Teacher Competence

The IHT training at Budi Mulia Karawang High School was interactive and hands-on. The training materials included in-depth learning, developing teaching modules, active learning strategies, and formative assessment. Teachers reported that the training method was interactive and very helpful in improving their understanding of teaching materials and learning strategies. Academic supervision is conducted through four stages: pre-observation, classroom observation, post-observation reflection, and follow-up. Supervisors stated that academic supervision is conducted in a planned manner through a supervision schedule and standardized observation instruments. Supervision results are used as a basis for improving learning strategies. Teachers report that the feedback provided is very helpful because it is constructive and helps them improve their learning practices.

Improving Teacher Performance in Learning Planning

Data shows that teachers' performance in developing teaching materials significantly improved after the implementation of IHT and supervision. Teachers became better able to develop teaching modules according to the curriculum structure, determine measurable learning objectives, design activities aligned with learning outcomes, and prepare relevant formative assessments. Interviews with students also indicated that teachers' teaching materials appeared more structured and used more consistently in class.

Improving Teacher Performance in Implementing Learning

Teachers demonstrated improved skills in implementing active learning strategies and using digital media. Supervisors stated that teachers began using varied methods and digital media as a result of the IHT program. The vice principal for curriculum added that ICT training was provided to support the use of technology in the classroom. Students also emphasized that teachers are using a variety of methods and digital media that are more engaging than before. Learning has become more varied and student oriented. This aligns with the school's in-depth learning goals.

Improving Teacher Performance in Learning Evaluation

Teachers demonstrated improvements in implementing formative assessments and follow-up learning. Remedial and enrichment programs became more systematic, supported by improved evaluation tools after the IHT. Supervisors stated that teachers were quite consistent in implementing formative assessments and remedial/enrichment programs. The principal also emphasized the importance of remedial and enrichment programs as part of the school's learning policy.

Synergy between IHT and Academic Supervision as a Mechanism for Teacher Professional Development.

Recent findings indicate that the synergy between IHT and academic supervision is a key factor in improving teacher performance. IHT provides a foundation of theoretical and technical skills, while academic supervision ensures the promotion of classroom implementation through reflective feedback and follow-up. The combination of the two creates a sustainable cycle that improves the quality of learning over time. Overall, this study shows that IHT and academic supervision have had a positive and significant impact on improving teacher performance at SMA Budi Mulia Karawang. Teachers not only experienced increased knowledge and skills but also improved professional attitudes, teaching practices, and use of digital media. However, performance improvement was not evenly distributed, as some teachers still needed further mentoring.

Discussion

The discussion of the research findings confirms that the implementation of In-House Training (IHT) and academic supervision at SMA Budi Mulia Karawang significantly contributed to improving teacher performance. The following discussion outlines the findings outlined in the research findings section and relates them to educational management theory and previous research.

Relevance of IHT Planning and Academic Supervision to Needs Analysis

The IHT planning and academic supervision conducted at SMA Budi Mulia Karawang are systematically structured based on a needs analysis obtained from educational reports, supervision results, and evaluation of teaching materials. This practice aligns with the principle of needs assessment in teacher professional development, which emphasizes that training must be based on real needs to be effective. As expressed in the theory of continuing professional development (Guskey, 2021), training programs designed without addressing teachers' actual needs will be less effective. In this school context, the development of IHT planning through the involvement of the principal,

supervisor, and vice principal for curriculum demonstrates the school management's commitment to improving teacher capacity. Teacher performance assessment has benefits for a school because this assessment will provide the level of achievement of standards, measures or criteria that have been set by the school. So that the weaknesses that exist in a teacher can be overcome and will provide feedback to the teacher. According to Mangkuprawira quoted (Kusmawan, 2025), the benefits of employee performance assessment are: (1) performance improvement; (2) compensation adjustment; (3) appointment decisions; (4) training and development needs; (5) career planning and development; (6) efficiency of the staff placement process; (7) inaccurate information; (8) job design errors; (9) equal employment opportunities; (10) external challenges; (11) feedback to HR.

Conformity of IHT Implementation with the Teacher Professional Development Model

The IHT program is interactive, applicable, and includes in-depth learning materials, the development of teaching modules, and formative assessments. Teachers reported that the training methods were very helpful and relevant to their needs. This is consistent with the characteristics of effective professional development according to (Darling-Hammond, 2021), namely ongoing training, involving hands-on practice, being work-based, and encouraging collaboration. The alignment between theory and practice at SMA Budi Mulia Karawang demonstrates that IHT is designed to provide skills that can be directly implemented in the classroom. IHT also serves as a means of aligning perceptions in the implementation of the Independent Curriculum, particularly in the development of teaching modules, learning objectives, and formative assessments. These findings reinforce Amalia in (Nuary, 2024) argument that contextual and sustainable IHT can improve teachers' abilities in designing active learning. According to Mulyasa, quoted (Ramli, 2024), he explains that there are at least ten factors that can improve teacher performance, both internal and external factors: These ten factors are: (1) motivation to work, (2) responsibility for tasks, (3) interest in tasks, (4) appreciation for tasks, (5) opportunities to develop, (6) attention from the principal, (7) interpersonal relationships with fellow teachers, (8) MGMP and KKG, (9) guided discussion groups and (10) library services.

Academic Supervision as a Mechanism for Continuous Mentoring

Academic supervision is conducted in four stages: pre-observation, classroom observation, reflection, and follow-up. Supervisors stated that supervision is conducted on a schedule and follows standardized instruments. Teachers also acknowledged receiving constructive feedback that helps them refine their teaching strategies. This aligns with (Sergiovanni & Starratt, 2018) concept of academic supervision, which emphasizes the importance of supervision as professional support to improve teaching quality, not merely administrative evaluation. The results of this study confirm that reflective supervision provides a space for teachers to understand their strengths and weaknesses and plan to improve the quality of learning. Supervisory follow-up is also a crucial factor in supporting changes in teaching behavior. The principal stated that teachers are required to improve their teaching based on written recommendations from supervisors. This ensures a continuous supervision cycle and has a tangible impact on teacher competency.

Improving Teacher Performance in Preparing Teaching Materials

Research findings show that teachers are increasingly able to develop teaching modules that are more comprehensive, structured, and aligned with the curriculum. This is reinforced by teachers' own statements that they are better able to develop teaching materials after participating in IHT. This increase demonstrates that IHT has a real impact on learning planning. According to (Priansa & Karwati, 2014), sound learning planning is the foundation of quality learning. By improving teachers' ability to design learning modules, the effectiveness of classroom learning also increases. Mulyasa, quoted (Rifky, 2024), explains the benefits of educational staff assessment: educational staff assessments are usually focused on individual achievement and their participation in school activities. This assessment is not only important for the school, but also for the educational staff concerned. For educational staff, assessments are useful as feedback on various things, abilities, accuracy, shortcomings, and potential which in turn are useful for determining goals, paths, plans, and career development. For schools, the results of educational staff performance assessments are very important in making decisions on various matters, such as identifying school program needs, admission, selection, introduction, placement, promotion, reward systems and other aspects of the overall human resource development process. Based on the description above, performance assessments are important for schools to improve teacher performance and for schools to develop new plans or strategies to achieve national education goals. These assessments can provide input for teachers in improving and enhancing their performance. Furthermore, teacher performance assessments help teachers better understand their tasks, enabling

them to implement learning as effectively as possible for the advancement of both students and teachers themselves toward becoming professional teachers.

Improving the Implementation of Active Method and ICT-Based Learning

Teachers began implementing active learning methods and utilizing digital media in their lessons after participating in IHT and supervision. Supervisors stated that teachers used varied methods and digital media more intensively, while students confirmed changes in teachers' methods and use of digital media. These findings support the research of (Wahyudi et al, 2024), which stated that the integration of IHT and academic supervision improves teachers' ability to use digital learning media. This improvement also aligns with the demands of the Independent Curriculum, which encourages active learning and technology integration.

Improving Learning Evaluation: Formative, Remedial, and Enrichment Assessments

Teachers demonstrated improved skills in implementing formative assessments and following up on student learning. This was evident in reports that teachers were implementing formative, remedial, and enrichment evaluations more consistently. The principal also emphasized that teachers are required to prepare remedial and enrichment programs as part of school policy. This demonstrates that learning evaluation is not merely an assessment tool but is used as a basis for decision-making in teaching. Surya in (Arifin, 2024) states that professional competence is the various abilities needed to realize oneself as a professional teacher, which includes expertise or expertise in one's field, namely mastery of the material to be taught and its methods, so that they can guide students to achieve predetermined competency standards. In carrying out their duties, teachers are required to have mastery of academic abilities and other skills that play a role in supporting teacher professionalism. These academic abilities include having the ability to master knowledge, having the ability to conduct scientific research that can support one's profession, mastering the insight and foundation of education. Meanwhile, skill ability is the ability to develop competencies to support one's profession.

Synergy of IHT and Supervision as a Model for Teacher Professional Development

The final discussion emphasized that teacher performance improvements do not occur spontaneously, but rather are the result of ongoing intervention through IHT and academic supervision. IHT provides conceptual understanding, while supervision ensures ongoing implementation through observation, reflection, and follow-up. This finding is consistent with the theory of Continuous Professional Development (Guskey, 2021), which explains that teacher competency improvement occurs through a continuous cycle of training, practice, and reflection. Collaboration with school management contributes to the success of this pattern, as evidenced by the results of curriculum supervision and coordination. This discussion confirms that the implementation of IHT and academic supervision at SMA Budi Mulia Karawang is highly effective in improving teacher competency in planning, implementing, and evaluating learning. The combination of training and mentoring has proven to be a sustainable model for teacher professional development and has a significant impact on learning quality.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and discussion regarding the implementation of In-House Training (IHT), academic supervision, and its improvement on teacher performance at SMA Budi Mulia Karawang, several main conclusions were obtained as follows: 1) IHT planning and academic supervision have been conducted systematically and based on a needs analysis. The school developed a program plan based on an analysis of educational report cards, the results of previous years' supervision, the condition of teachers' teaching materials, and the needs for implementing the Independent Curriculum. The planning included establishing goals, objectives, materials, resource persons, schedules, and budgets. This demonstrates that school management has implemented the principles of needs assessment as a basis for teacher professional development, 2) The implementation of IHT plays a significant role in improving teacher competency, particularly in developing teaching materials and developing a deeper understanding of learning. IHT has had a positive impact on improving teachers' abilities in developing teaching modules, designing learning objectives, using active learning models, and understanding formative assessment. Teachers feel IHT is relevant because the material is tailored to the context and learning needs at SMA Budi Mulia Karawang, 3) Academic supervision works effectively as a professional mentoring mechanism. Supervision is conducted through pre-observation, observation, reflection, and follow-up stages. Teachers receive constructive and comprehensive feedback to improve their teaching practices. Supervision serves as both an evaluative and coaching tool that strengthens the implementation of IHT results in the classroom, 4) Teacher

performance improved in three aspects: planning, implementation, and evaluation of learning. Teachers became more skilled at developing comprehensive and structured teaching materials, applying active and technology-based learning methods, and conducting formative, remedial, and enrichment assessments more systematically. Teacher performance improved, particularly among teachers who actively participated in the IHT and implemented follow-up supervision, 5) The synergy of IHT and academic supervision has proven to be an effective professional development model. IHT provides the theoretical and practical foundation, while supervision ensures consistent implementation. The combination of the two creates a continuous development cycle that has significantly impacted the quality of learning and teacher professionalism at SMA Budi Mulia Karawang.

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